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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.36811/jca.2021.110030>

JCA: November-2021: Page No: 833-873

Universal Journal of Chemistry and Applications

Review Article

Open Access

Therapeutic Potential of Pharmacological Targeting NLRP3 Inflammasome Complex in Cancer Using Inhibition of NLRP3 Inflammasome in Tumor Microenvironment Leads to Suppression of Metastatic Potential of Cancer Cells

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Received Date: Sep 16, 2021 / **Accepted Date:** Nov 08, 2021 / **Published Date:** Nov 11, 2021

Abstract

Thanks to work by researchers at the California South University (CSU) Cancer Research Institute (CRI), they may soon have new tools to treat melanoma and other cancers. In an article published last month, members of the Cancer Research Institute (CRI) introduced an intracellular complex. Involved in melanoma-mediated inflammation and leads to tumor growth and progression. The researchers found that by inhibiting NLRP3, they could reduce inflammation and tumor spread.

Keywords: Cancer; Cells; Tissues, Tumors; Prevention, Prognosis; Diagnosis; Imaging; Screening; Treatment; Management

Cite this article as: Alireza Heidari, Elena Locci, Silvia Raymond. 2021. Therapeutic Potential of Pharmacological Targeting NLRP3 Inflammasome Complex in Cancer Using Inhibition of NLRP3 Inflammasome in Tumor Microenvironment Leads to Suppression of Metastatic Potential of Cancer Cells. J Chem Appl. 3: 833-873.

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Introduction

In particular, NLRP3 induces inflammation by maturing and releasing interleukin-1-beta (a cytokine that triggers inflammation as part of

the natural immune response to infection). In cancer, however, inflammation can cause tumors to grow and spread. According to one of the researchers in this study, NLRP3 is a member of a larger family that is involved in sensing danger signals. It is a receptor that

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looks for TB intercellular cells and risk molecules or pathogens. When NLRP3 detects these signals, it activates caspase-1, a protein involved in the processing and maturation of interleukin-1. Beta, in its biologically active form, causes a severe inflammatory reaction. We found that in melanoma, this process is not regulated and leads to tumor growth. The NLRP3 oral inhibitor shown in this study is effective in clinical trials for the treatment of gout and heart disease and is currently being tested on Covid-19. Researchers at the Cancer Research Institute (CRI) are now trying to find out if this NLRP3 inhibitor can be used successfully in melanoma patients who are resistant to checkpoint inhibitors. Researchers say checkpoint inhibitors increase the immune system's ability to kill tumors, but sometimes tumors become resistant to the treatment. A major part of cancer research now is finding treatments that can be combined with checkpoint inhibitors to improve their effectiveness [1-510].

Results and Discussion

Hypothesizing that NLRP3 inhibitors are one of these treatments, researchers at the California South University (CSU) Cancer Research Institute (CRI) are studying the effects of the drug on melanoma, as well as breast cancer and pancreatic cancer. In addition to improving the immune response, NLRP3 inhibitors can also help reduce the side effects of checkpoint inhibitors. This research can make a big difference for melanoma patients who do not respond only to checkpoint inhibitors.

Conclusions

This project is important because it further demonstrates that NLRP3-induced inflammation plays an important role in the development of melanoma and opens up new strategies for improving patient care.

Acknowledgment

This study was supported by the Cancer Research Institute (CRI) Project of Scientific Instrument and Equipment Development, the National Natural Science Foundation of the United States, the International Joint Bio Spectroscopy Core Research Laboratory Program supported by the California South University (CSU), and the Key project supported by the American International Standards Institute (AIS), Irvine, California, USA.

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Biguanide, Polyhexamethylene Adipamide, Polyhexamethylene Biguanide Gauze and Polyhexamethylene Biguanide Hydrochloride (PHMB) Boron Nitride Nanotubes (BNNTs), Amorphous Boron Nitride Nanotubes (a-BNNTs) and Hexagonal Boron Nitride Nanotubes (h-BNNTs). *J Appl Computat Math.* 5: 143.

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